

How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?

Scenario Study

Assignment submitted by

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| INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST |

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COURSE	INTERNATIONAL CERTIFIED FUTURE STRATEGIST 2021
ASSIGNMENT	HOME ASSIGNMENT #2
SUBJECT	SCENARIO ANALYSIS AND FORMULATION
GOAL	Use the course's knowledge in a specific scenario analysis that describes possible future developments.
TASK	Make a scenario study for a real case, where the methods that have been examined during the course are used, including factor spotting, factor analysis and scenario formulation. The case is a continuation from assignment 1.
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1 Executive Summary

This report was submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the [International Future Strategist Certification Programme](#) by KAIROS. It is the second of three assignments and aims to replicate an actual case study. The case presented herein is an actual case and although it does not involve at this stage a wide participation of stakeholders, hopefully it creates a good starting point for further research.

The subject is **innovation** and the question around which the research evolves is “**How will the Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?**”. What can we expect from it? What are the key factors, both trends and uncertainties that impact it, how are they interrelated and how important are they?

This **report builds upon the findings of the previous stage (HA1 Report)** that covered the first stage of the foresight study: the environmental scanning and trends analysis. Given the time and resources restriction, this is done using simple tools of analysis: desk research, online libraries, open data and simple visualisations. Only a limited engagement of few stakeholders was possible at this stage mainly through feedback in already identified factors. A virtual [collaborative space serves](#) as a showcase of the findings and an easy way for providing comments and insights.

The **report contains:**

- An **executive summary** with the most important issues covered and an **introduction** reminding the context, the focal question and the client and purpose.
- A short **description of the trends and uncertainties** that were examined in assignment 1 and a comprehensive picture to what direction will the specific trends develop from today until the target year. Several uncertain trends presented with (two) possible future developments (outcomes) each (polarization).
- A **scenario matrix** and deeper description of the **scenarios** in the matrix.
- A **table of characteristics** and an “**Early Warning Table**” to assess which scenario will become a reality.

	<p><i>Do you want to contribute?</i></p> <p>If you would like to access the collaborative space used in this report and give feedback you can access it without the need for login here: https://bit.ly/InnoGreece2 You can use the comment feature to provide any kind of feedback, thought or insight.</p>
	<p><i>Feedback & Comments in this report</i></p> <p>You can check the previous report here .</p>

2 Introduction

Innovation is vital to the growth and prosperity of our society. It is the use of new ideas, products, or methods in areas that have not been used before. (Eurostat, 2012) Innovation is not restricted to technology or science. It permeates every sector and step of the production and distribution process.

The focal question of the study is **How will Greek innovation ecosystem evolve by 2035?** We examine not innovation in a specific industry or sector but rather, the process of innovation. How have Greece and EU promoted and will promote innovation and support new ideas that can lead to economic development and growth.

The **timeframe** expands beyond current framework programmes and initiatives (Horizon Europe), **Next Generation Europe**, **Greece 2.0** and will help be better prepared for the next generation of funding and initiatives.

The **primary purpose** of the study is to help the client, **International Development Ireland Ltd. (IDI)** identify opportunities in Greece and in the area, find new services in innovation support that will be needed by the private and public sector and even examine the possibility of establishing a new innovation hub or a regional office in the area.

The first part of the exercise (HA#1) identified the **trends and uncertainties** and ran a first analysis of driving forces and consequences. A cross impact analysis of these trends and uncertainties provided a map of their relationships and helped reach some very useful insights:

- EU is moving fast towards **Green and Digital transformation** making the related trends all too important. To this end, EU will invest significant funds.
- The **pandemic served as an accelerator** in Greece with new digital services introduced by the government almost monthly.
- Despite initial resistance EU approved for the first time a **common debt instrument (Next Generation EU Fund)** to support the **COVID19 recovery**.
- We decided to focus on the **Greek Innovation ecosystem**, however, it is **strongly interrelated to the EU one**. We cannot study one without the other.
- Lastly, we should remember that as of Dec 2021, nothing is over yet. The new O variant looms, SE Europe and the Balkans remain sensitive areas. Relations between Turkey and Greece are tensed. Fall of Afghanistan will probably create new migrant flows.

In this document we progress use the trends and uncertainties to develop four scenarios for the future and describe the possible outcomes.

EU's R&I programmes

In the next 7 years (2021-2027), EU has approved a budget where the support of R&I through various programmes is center staged.

(2021-2027 Long-Term EU Budget & NextGenerationEU | European Commission, n.d.) Horizon Europe is the biggest EU research and Innovation (R&I) support initiative, but there are a lot more other programmes that also support innovation and a green and digital transition, like Digital Europe, Erasmus+, Interregional Innovation Investments, Innovation Fund, Single Market Programme and of course the Next Generation EU fund to support EU member states in their COVID19 recovery. *(2021-2027 Long-*

International Development Ireland (IDI)

A provider of innovation support, capacity building and technical assistance to public and private organisations. [www.idi.ie]

3 Trends and Uncertainties

In the previous report (HA#1) we examined the trends and uncertainties and ran a cross impact analysis that led to some interesting conclusions and prioritisation of the critical trends. Based on our analysis we identified five (5) major trends and mapped their driving forces and their consequences:

- A **consistent drop of computing costs** in the long term, despite the recent disruption in the semiconductor market and the shortage of chips.
- An **acceleration of digitisation**, partly thanks to COVID19 and a new “low touch” economy that moves even more transactions online.
- A renewed **climate change awareness**, reinforced by a dreadful summer of fires and environmental destruction especially in the south.
- A **shortage of skills** especially for specific, advanced, and highly in demand skills and soft, horizontal skills necessary for all.
- A **sharing economy** that is expected to grow from \$15 billion in 2014 to \$335 billion in 2025. (Tabcum, 2019)

TREND ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES			
DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	TREND	CONSEQUENCES What does the trend lead to?	HYPOTHESES Long term consequences?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Declining costs of computing - Expanding of connectivity - Declining costs in Telecom - Need for constant connectivity 	Affordable XaaS Lowering prices of online services and plethora of available tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More accessible computing for startups allows easier implementation of their ideas. - Close to zero costs for infrastructure. - New business models and services for both B2C, B2B 	Businesses and consumers move to a model where almost everything is offered as a Service (XaaS). Traditional ownership models decline.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for further efficiency - Strive for cost reduction - Promise for a better/ faster/ cheaper service/ product. - Inevitable future (Digitise or perish) 	Digitisation Acceleration Transformation of Analog into digital for every aspect of business, life, government.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New or improved services/ products - Interaction between business < - > governments - Ability for deep analysis (Big Data, AI) - Preservation of Information & Knowledge - Easier Disaster Recovery - Income generation from new ideas, business 	Every business is a digital business. Digitisation facilitates integration of different business verticals through industries blending together and merging. Physical and Digital spaces are blurred. Major consequences in the future of work and life.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Climate Change Awareness Global warming, extreme weather, biodiversity loss, scarcity of resources are acknowledged as major problems. Actions taken by governments & businesses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governments and International organisation taking initiatives and imposing new regulations - Businesses adopt environmentally responsible policies (ESG a requirement) - Citizens and consumers demand policies / actions. - Shift to renewable energy, decarbonisation, nuclear (?) 	Hopefully, immediate dangers are mitigated. Long term strategy by International Organisations (UN) leads to some valid results. However, danger is not easily averted. Some countries are more affected than others. Shift of agriculture production North since South too hot.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experience of extreme phenomena in everyday life - A new generation more environmentally responsible - Global Activism (Greta) - Compounding scientific proof 	Skills Shortages Lack of necessary technical and soft skills from workforce. Low interest of young generations to pursue these more demanding skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less and less well trained people available for demanding and challenging works. - Lower quality workforce - Scarcity of specific skills, capabilities and experiences. - Ruthless competition for talent between corporations and smaller businesses 	Disruption of traditional education models. New corporate training and continuous learning are adopted. Companies provide initiatives for training into certain skills similar to military (guarantee payments, tax incentives, insurance etc.)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internet communities/ networks - Mobile economy (apps) - Decentralisation - Resource Efficiency 	Sharing Economy boom Wide adoption of new work models of sharing economy, peer-to-peer networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New decentralised networks and collaboration opportunities - Increased efficiency of resource usage - Changes in the work models 	New models of ownership and work. You do not need to own (almost) anything when you can easily find it through a network.

In addition to the trends, we have also identified several more long-term **uncertainties** that we believe will impact our path to the future. With the

pandemic still looming and new dangerous variants already in circulation, the situation is still unstable and unpredictable.

We already see high inflation, a spike in energy prices in Europe, partly because of Russia's geopolitical game, and a major supply chain disruption. However, we believe that these are reactions from a restart of a global economy after more than one year of strict lockdowns, rather than long term persistent trends that will prevail in the long run.

We believe that the 5 identified trends will move upwards, meaning that

UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF DRIVING FORCES AND CONSEQUENCES			
DRIVING FORCES What makes the trend happen?	UNCERTAINTY	OUTCOMES	CONSEQUENCES What does each outcome lead to?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A new financial crisis - Unchecked inflation - Cost of climate change - Geopolitical Reasons 	Financial Environment Global, European and Greek economy.	A leap forward: Innovation Europe EU respond swiftly with a common strategy and make a leap forward by investing in innovation.	EU and Greece see the new crisis as an opportunity for further actions to support innovation & position as a global player.
		Surviving the next crisis EU steps up but not enough. Innovation is no longer a priority. EU still cannot agree on a common strategy.	Greece cannot realise its plans without enough EU support. The environment is not good for supporting new ideas and startups amidst a global crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Geopolitical Environment Situation in SE Europe and M.East.	A frail peace Status quo continuous with no major changes. EU takes a bigger role in the area. New alliances and active EU (France), USA role, deter aggressiveness.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation.
		Sporadic microcrisis There is no major crisis but sporadic smaller conflicts and standoffs, inhibit growth and cost a lot.	Greece navigates and tries to insulate its economy and society from these crisis but the instability of the area holds back major investments from abroad (FDI).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unresolved Issues - Authoritarian States - Injustice and poverty - New Civil wars - Refugee & Migration - Turkey's attitude 	Role of Government How Greek administration responds to the challenges of the environment and what long term vision it creates.	A vision for the future Government adopts an ambitious vision for the future and manages to implement it successfully.	Greece establishes a new diplomacy, based on soft power and strong alliances with major players. Defence sector embraces innovation.
		A vision without actions Vision is there but cannot be realised or it becomes a half baked version mired with more problems than solutions.	Government succumbs to populism and does not go through with necessary structural changes. Populist parties disrupt the political space creating a new crisis.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - COVID19 persistence - Demands by employees - Social Insecurity - New work habits - Drive for Digital Nomads - Bussines Real Estate 	Workplace future Changes in the workplace, WFH.	A destination for Digital Nomads Greece becomes top destination for attracting talent and building new synergies between them and local ecosystem.	Digital Nomads become the bridge to link local innovation ecosystem with global players. A whole sector and ecosystem is build around this notion.
		Digital Nomads potential unutilized Digital Nomads come but no added value created. Only a useful tourism product.	Digital Nomads remain indifferent and uninterested in the Greek Innovation ecosystem. Innovation stakeholders cannot benefit from their presence.

we can expect cheaper computing power, more digitisation, further environmental awareness, and more green investments.

Shortage of skills will continue to be an issue since the pace of technology and science discoveries is neck breaking and the innovation cycles shorter and shorter.

Unfortunately, there is still a wildcard in the table. **COVID19 is far from over** and it affects every single aspect of life and society compounding existing and creating new uncertainties. Most analysts expect that situation will normalize within the next 2 years (by 2023) but the unprecedented level of disruption and distraction the pandemic brought will certainly have a long-term effect and impact in a lot more aspects and ways we can imagine today.

4 Scenarios for the future

The identification of the trends and uncertainties and their analysis and documentation brings us one step closer to the formation of a structure to better understand the possible futures. The polarization of the most critical uncertainties is a very important step of the process. It will reveal the extremes and will allow us to explore the worst- and best-case outcomes. We chose 4 to polarize 4 uncertainties: **Economy, Geopolitics, Governance, Globalisation**.

Having identified these extreme outcomes for these key uncertainties, we can then proceed to the next step of scenario development: Scenario combinations where we can test alternative structures and test the logics

of scenarios. Four (4) combinations were tested as seen in the diagram below. All of them provided challenging outcomes and fascinating scenarios. We chose combination 4: Economy X Governance because we believe that these are the ones that can provide us with some actionable strategies.

Why we chose the economy and governance?

After a financial crisis that lasted for almost 10 years and a political instability that led to a toxic polarization of society and politics, Greece is finally taking some long overdue steps. Much needed reforms, accelerated by the pandemic, are under way and Greece is emerging as a global soft power actor (Greece 2021: Emerging Global Soft Power Actor | Wall Street International Magazine, n.d.). This positive trend can be attributed to a much better **governance**, a term that in our context includes both the political situation in the country, the legislative and the executive initiatives, the medium and short term planning and its implementation from the government and the public sector.

On the other hand, the selection of **economy** (both at the EU level and in Greece) does not need a lot of explanation. Without solid and sound financials we cannot expect initiatives for innovation and long-term vision. The country, the society and businesses operate in survival mode, as they did for the most part of the last decade.

With this in mind, we worked with these 2 axes and with their extremes:

- From **Stagflation** and **financial crisis** to **Strong Economic Growth**.
- From **Protectionist, Populist, and introvert governance** (and government) to an **Open, Pro-Market** and **pro-business** Government.

The scenario table above can be better understood in combination with the table of characteristics below, where we can see how different factors play out in the respective scenarios.

FACTOR/ ASPECT	The Star	The Bubble	Endless Crisis	Endurance
Role of EU Institutions	High	High	Medium	Low
Digitisation Acceleration	Catalyst	Follower	Observer	Opportunity
Climate Awareness	Innovative Cross Sector Synergies	Compliance	Indifference, Low priority	Pragmatic Investments, Responsiveness
Health & Safety	Vaccination, Underlying Protocols	Reform resistance	Low trust on science	New safety habits
Geopolitical Situation	Determination and deterance	Hoping for external support	Crisis Management	Looking for allies
Society	Supportive and participating	Short term benefits	Blame game	Enduring
Level of Trust	High	Low	Very Low	Medium

Future developments are never linear. One single scenario almost never becomes the reality. It is usually a more complicated and intermingled process where we get variations and combinations of different outcomes. However, usually, a direction is obvious. A tool to identify such a direction and adapt accordingly our future foresights or rethink our strategy is the **Early Warning Table**.

Early Warning Table (What indicates that a scenario is about to come true?)

FACTOR/ ASPECT	The Star	The Bubble	Endless Crisis	Endurance
EU State of the Union	Stronger Integration	Agreements in Principle, Common Understanding	Dangerous Rifts, New polemic against EU	Disagreements but collaborative spirit
Technology & Digitisation	Digitisation level of country, telecoms	Lack of serious infrastructure, short term projects	Lack of interest, disengagement	Conservative approach in digitisation
Climate Change & Environment	New cross sectoral innovations	Understanding but reluctance for serious actions	Crisis management without prevention mechanisms	Willingness but lack of funds
Health emergencies	High levels of vaccination, restored freedoms	Acceptance of post COVID19 situation	Inability to handle simple situations	Move towards personal responsibility
Geopolitical Situation in SE Europe	Strong collaboration between defence & R&D	Major investments but uncoordinated and often low value	Mistakes of the past	Working with less
Society	Buy in of a new vision	Going for short term benefits	Corruption	Painful maturing
Level of Trust	increase of trust in elites and science	Distrust but compliance	Complete lack of trust to the system	Trust and hope

4.1 Scenario 1: The Star

Since its last existential crisis that lasted almost a decade between 2010-2019, the country has reinvented itself increasing its global soft power and improving its performance in almost every single index. From one of the problematic countries of the EU, Greece managed to become a model of stability, reliability, and governance. This does not mean that all challenges or problems have disappeared. Greece has still unresolved problems caused by the aggressiveness of Turkey, its trade deficit is still negative and has an ageing population. However, since 2020 the country has implemented significant structural reforms with large privatizations of state enterprises which attracted major foreign direct investment (FDI) and created strong links with universities and R&D centres. At least five major innovation hubs have emerged in Athens (Capital), Thessaloniki (North), Iraklion (South), Ioannina and Patras (West) with more under way. These hubs have worked on a robust regional innovation strategy

and created opportunities for a clear diversification of the economy in sectors other than tourism, like agrifood, maritime, renewables, smart health. In addition to these sectors the national defense industry is revitalized, and the public welfare system is reformed with larger participation of the private sector and establishment of private pension funds. The spark for these changes can be traced back in the global health crisis caused by COVID-19 and the Turkish aggressiveness and provocations in the Aegean Sea and SE Europe between 2020 to 2025. The country seems to be in the right track at last.

4.2 Scenario 2: Endurance

The country has gone a long way since its last extended financial and political crisis that lasted almost a decade. All governments since then have understood the importance of innovation and entrepreneurship and have made all (or at least most) necessary reforms to attract investments and new capital. The country is today a reliable and trustworthy partner with longstanding strategic partnerships with France, USA, Israel, S. Arabia, UAE, Egypt. These partnerships, originally framed around defense and military support, were expanded in innovation and entrepreneurship support in sectors like health, ICT, space, energy, agrifood. The innovation ecosystem is growing and all four major actors in the innovation system: R&I and academic institutions, policy makers, industry and society are engaged and active.

Unfortunately, the EU is still struggling to find its place in the global geopolitical arena and speak with one voice against Russia's aggression and China's expansionist policy. High inflation and energy prices are still causing disruptions in the global value chains. Disagreements in EU foreign policy frequently lead to political arm wrestling between member states and delays in distribution of EU structural and R&I funds. This creates a major problem for Greece since it does not allow the country to reach its full potential. Despite the obstacles and the lost opportunities, the innovation ecosystem is enduring and has found a path forward.

4.3 Scenario 3: The bubble

A simple visit in one of the big Greek cities makes pretty obvious that the country is not in crisis anymore. In the last decade, after the world recovered from the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism has grown bigger than ever before, and the construction sector is once more driving the economy. Disposable income appears abundant and retail spending is quite high. Inflation runs high but it's counterbalanced by the abundant flow of money through newly created initiatives, funds, and support to businesses. However, funds are not directed to reforming the economy and investments go to sectors with fast returns while infrastructures are not getting their share. After 4-5 year of structural reforms in the public sector, the welfare system, and fiscal policies, it seems that both the

political system and society have lost their interest for meaningful changes and black (unrecorded and untaxed) economy is gaining ground again.

It almost seems like the lessons from the big Greek crisis of 2010-2020 are forgotten and people lost their will for any kind of change. Populists are rising again, benefiting from the global political uncertainty, the communication problems in the EU and push from unions and society.

In this environment, the innovation ecosystem has access to money but not the necessary reforms and supporting mechanisms it needs to grow. So, although money is flowing in, there is lack of due diligence, poor governance and signs of corruption and malpractice across the innovation value chain, making the situation resembling more a kind of bubble than a healthy innovation ecosystem.

5 Conclusion

If we learned something during the years of pandemic, is that predicting the future is impossible. We can only study the developments and try to be better prepared. The situation is still extremely unstable and unpredictable, which means that our planning needs to be dynamic.

There are a lot of positive signs for Greece and its innovation space but at the same time we realise that the situation is still extremely fluid. The appearance of the new Omicron variant, the persisting inflation, the geopolitical games with energy in Europe and the post pandemic supply chain challenges are all complex wildcards that we cannot easily predict.

Nevertheless, we have our ideal scenario, and we can develop a strategy that could lead into its realization.

6 References

2021-2027 long-term EU budget & NextGenerationEU | European Commission. (n.d.). Retrieved December 22, 2021, from https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027_en

Eurostat. (2012). *Glossary: Innovation.* Statistics Explained.
Greece 2021: emerging global soft power actor | Wall Street International Magazine. (n.d.). Retrieved December 27, 2021, from <https://wsimag.com/economy-and-politics/64544-greece-2021-emerging-global-soft-power-actor>

Tabcum, S. Jr. (2019). *The Sharing Economy Is Still Growing, And Businesses Should Take Note.* Forbes.
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbeslacouncil/2019/03/04/the-sharing-economy-is-still-growing-and-businesses-should-take-note/?sh=385eabd84c33>

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